

COMET Projects

Documentation

Match Preprints to Published Journal Articles

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Introduction

Purpose

Welcome to the project documentation for the [COMET](#) project *Match Preprints to Published Journal Articles*. This open document serves a dual purpose:

- **Documentation hub for ongoing projects:** providing a comprehensive overview of the project goals, opportunities for community participation, and status updates as the project progresses.
- **Provenance record for completed projects:** containing a report of the project results, linked outputs such as the enrichment methods and datasets, and an assessment of the project outcomes.

Get involved

This project is complete. Explore the result report and access the enrichments via the DataCite enrichments API.

Cite this project

Any references to this project should be cited as: Collaborative Metadata (COMET) . (2025). *COMET Project: Match Preprints to Published Journal Articles*. Collaborative Metadata (COMET). <https://doi.org/10.82461/m8a8-m211>

Find enriched DOI metadata from this project

All enriched datasets produced by this project are listed in the *Project outputs* section. Any enrichments to DataCite metadata can be explored through the DataCite enrichments API ([support documentation](#)).

Funding and support

This project is supported with in-kind contributions from the COMET Organisers representing the California Digital Library, CWTS at the Leiden University, DataCite, and the Public Knowledge Project. Support for COMET's enrichment projects, which leverage DataCite metadata, has been provided to DataCite by The Navigation Fund through award ID doi.org/10.71707/yj21-5d60.

Project Overview

Project objective

We're developing automated tools to connect preprints with their corresponding published journal articles, piloting the approach with preprints in the arXiv repository, to improve knowledge on how research moves from early sharing to formal publication.

Why this matters

Currently, when researchers share preprints on arXiv and later publish the same work in a journal, these two versions exist as isolated records in different systems. In the pilot example, arXiv preprints receive DataCite DOIs, whilst journal articles primarily receive Crossref DOIs, but there's no systematic way to know that these DOIs refer to different versions of the same research. This disconnect creates several critical problems for the research ecosystem such as underestimating research output and impact in reporting and assessment processes.

The approach

We're using a comprehensive automated matching approach, building on the successful work already done by Crossref, that combines multiple identification strategies to connect preprints with their published versions.

The data inputs include:

- **1.4 million arXiv DOIs** from DataCite that currently lack connections to published versions
- **Crossref journal article metadata** to identify potential matches in the published literature
- **Multiple metadata fields** including titles, authors, and other identifying information to ensure accurate connections

We're measuring success through several key outcomes:

- **Connected Records:** Successfully linking arXiv preprints to their published journal articles
- **Precision and Recall Metrics:** Achieving high accuracy in matching whilst minimising false connections that could mislead researchers about research relationships
- **Processing Efficiency:** demonstrating scalability for ongoing use

Expected results

This project aims to produce:

- Benchmark datasets and strategy performance metrics
- A dataset containing identified links between arXiv DOIs and publisher DOIs

Who benefits

Improving the links between research outputs can have many benefits, such as:

- **Researchers** can easily discover whether preprints have been published and track the complete impact of their work across both preprint and publication venues
- **Academic Institutions** gain visibility into the full research pipeline of their faculty, improving institutional reporting and understanding research development timelines
- **Research Libraries** can provide more comprehensive discovery services, helping users find all versions of research and understand publication relationships
- **Funding Agencies** receive more complete pictures of how supported research develops from early sharing through formal publication, enabling better assessment of research impact and timeline
- **Publishers and Journals** can better understand how their publications relate to the broader preprint ecosystem and track research development patterns.

Project status

Project phases

Phase description	Phase status
Plan scope with project partners	Completed ▾
Create gold-standard benchmark dataset	Completed ▾
Implement matching strategy based on existing Crossref strategy	Completed ▾
Test and refine strategy	Completed ▾
Publish result and share with community for feedback	Completed ▾
Assess project in collaboration with community members	Completed ▾
Ingest the enriched metadata to the DataCite enrichment layer	Completed ▾

Progress updates record

- 4 Sept, 2025: Publish results report
- 10 Sept, 2025: Publish end-of-project assessment community invite
- 26 Sept, 2025: Conduct project assessment (with project team)
- 3 Oct, 2025 Conduct project assessment (with community)
- 25 Oct, 2025: Begin roundtripping prototype with DataCite
- 22 April, 2026: Enrichments available through DataCite enrichments API.

Project collaborators

Organisations, initiatives, and groups

#	Name	ROR ID (when applicable)	Role (DataCite: contributorType)	List as Creator? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
1	COMET (Collaborative Metadata)	NA	NA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2	California Digital Library	https://ror.org/03yrm5c26	Sponsor ▾	
3	CWTS, Leiden University	https://ror.org/027bh9e22	Sponsor ▾	
4	DataCite	https://ror.org/04wxnsj81	Sponsor ▾	
5	Public Knowledge Project	https://ror.org/05ek4tb53	Sponsor ▾	

Individuals

Full name (with ORCID)	Affiliation (# row above)	Role (DataCite: contributorType)	Role (NISO Credit taxonomy)	List as Creator? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Dione Mentis (0000-0001-6175-5683)	1, 4	ProjectManager ▾	Project administr... ▾ Writing – original ... ▾	
Adam Buttrick (0000-0003-1507-1031)	1, 2	ProjectLeader ▾	Conceptualisation ▾ Methodology ▾	
Ludo Waltman (0000-0001-8249-1752)	3	ProjectMember ▾	Formal analysis ▾	

Project outputs

Resource	Type	Link or File
The enrichment method	Source Code ▾	10.82461/S678-CV26 View in DataCite Commons
arXiv matching results	Dataset ▾	Zenodo: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15882986 HuggingFace: Link
Slides from the COMET Community meeting 15 July 2025 presenting the results	Document ▾	COMETCommunityMeeting_15July...

Project results report

Summary

The COMET initiative successfully developed an automated matching strategy to connect arXiv preprints with corresponding journal article publications, achieving 95–96% precision and 90% recall. The project increased preprint-to-publication connections from 45% to 71%, adding over 730,000 new connections to the scholarly record, improving research discoverability and interconnection.

Project background

arXiv has served as a foundational platform for rapid research dissemination for over three decades. Since 2022, approximately 1.4 million arXiv preprints have been registered with DataCite DOIs, creating the opportunity to track relationships between preprints and any published forms of these works. This development further embeds arXiv preprints into the broader scholarly infrastructure ecosystem, allowing for more systematic tracking and citation. However, at the start of this project, only 50% of DataCite DOI records for arXiv preprints contained links to subsequently published versions of these works, relying on voluntary author updates and variable publisher data feeds for these connections to be made. Although there was no automated system for creating these connections, the proven success of [a related method used in the Crossref context](#) highlighted the opportunity for COMET to build and validate a similar service for arXiv preprint DOIs registered with DataCite.

Methodology

The project began by adapting Crossref's [Search Based Matching with Validation \(SBMV\) strategy](#), chosen for its robust, benchmarked, and reproducible methodology. The initial approach involved inverting Crossref's existing strategy to match from preprints to published articles rather than the reverse direction.

This first attempt yielded high precision but low recall, identifying four matching cases between preprints and published articles for improvement: title variations, author name discrepancies, author list changes, and publication timing gaps. These were addressed by:

- **Improved title matching:** Enhanced string normalisation and implemented multiple fuzzy matching algorithms to accommodate title variations including reordering, additions, and substantial changes.
- **Sophisticated author handling:** Developed pairwise comparison methods generating multiple name variants to handle differences in formatting and efficiently process large author lists.
- **Flexible temporal scoring:** Introduced a weighted scoring system for publication year differences, allowing for longer but less common delays between a preprint release and a subsequent article publication.
- **Automated optimisation:** Used grid search techniques to test various weight combinations for titles, authors, and year gaps, optimising for precision and F0.5 scores.
- **Weighted scoring system:** Implemented a re-weighting mechanism with configurable parameters (title weight: 2.0, author weight: 0.8, year weight: 0.4, minimum score: 0.85) to identify the best matches based on optimisation results.

Results

The refined strategy delivered substantial improvements across all key metrics:

- **Precision:** 95-96% (matches found were highly accurate)
- **Recall:** 90% (successfully identified the vast majority of true matches)
- **Coverage improvement:** Increased connected preprints from 45% to 71% (+26% improvement)
- **New connections:** Added over 730,000 previously missing preprint-to-publication links

These results represent a significant enhancement to research discovery infrastructure, substantially improving the ability to trace scientific work through its complete publication

lifecycle. The dataset of new connections with corresponding confidence scores is published at: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15882986

Validation

The reliability of results was confirmed through two independent validation approaches:

- **Cross-reference with OpenAlex:** Comparison with OpenAlex's matching results showed approximately two-thirds overlap, with convergence from an independent source reinforcing result reliability.
- **Crossref benchmark testing:** The refined strategy was tested against Crossref's original benchmark dataset and achieved equivalent precision and recall, demonstrating generalisability without performance degradation.

Next steps

COMET is working with arXiv and DataCite to prototype a roundtripping solution so that these new connections to published works can be incorporated into the DOI metadata.

The matching strategy could be extended to other content types registered with DataCite or adjusted to apply to other preprint repositories.

We encourage the community to engage with the methodology and results and share their perspectives on the future direction of this strategy.

Project Assessment

Assessment Framework 1: Enacting the COMET Model

1. Trust and Transparency

Core Question: Is this pilot building community trust through open infrastructure and processes, and avenues for collective governance?

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
Project information, methodology and decisions are publicly documented and easily accessible for community review	This Project Hub document	“This document is very useful!”
Project outputs are published openly with provenance indicators and with sufficient detail to replicate.	Refer to the Resource tab for links to: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Datasets published on HuggingFace and Zenodo• Matching strategy registered as a DOI, providing provenance detail.• Code repo README	
Project reporting includes both successes, failures, and limitations	The results report includes a description of low recall in the first attempt of the strategy and how this was resolved.	

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
Community members participate in project assessment session	4 community members registered to join (as of 26 Sept)	

2. Community Stewardship and Engagement

Core Question: Is this pilot demonstrating the potential for shared responsibility in metadata quality with meaningful community support?

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
At least 2 community stakeholders (in addition to COMET organizers) participate in project	Yes, Ludo Waltman (CSWT) reviewed the matching strategy and its results, and Stephanie Orphan (arXiv) consulted during project	“What are the criteria for participation in the project?”
Community feedback demonstrates they value the enriched metadata or enrichment process produced by the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive feedback in the COMET Community Meeting (15 July) • 62 downloads of the enrichment dataset on Zenodo (as of 26 Sept) • Positive responses to COMET’s LinkedIn and Bluesky posts (likes/claps/reposts) 	“Can also track citations of the dataset and process”
Stakeholder engagement includes diversity across relevant dimensions (e.g.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on Community Meeting (15 July attendance, when results 	“Global North focus at the stage is expected and

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
geography, organisational size, discipline, and under-represented communities)	of this project were shared, there's strong European (70%) and North American (28%) engagement.	it will take time and effort to expand interest"

3. Collective Benefit Realisation

Core Question: Is this pilot creating value that could scale and benefit the broader research and scholarly communications ecosystem?

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
Clear demonstration of effectiveness for the specific metadata field and content type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Over 730K connections (relatedIdentifiers) between arXiv preprint DOI records and published articles found. Strategy has 95%+ precision and can be rerun as arxiv corpus grows. 	
Evidence of de-siloing metadata enrichments (either the process or the metadata itself)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The openly published strategy can be adapted to work for other preprint servers. 	
At least 2 stakeholders express interest in using the enrichment dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 62 downloads of the enrichment dataset on Zenodo (as of 26 Sept) 	

4. Ecosystem Integration Effectiveness

Core Question: Are we establishing viable pathways for enrichments to flow back to authoritative sources?

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
At least 1 integration pathway is planned with documented approach	DataCite is piloting providing enriched records (via API) using the dataset from this project (see DataCite Open Hours announcement from min 41:54). Documentation for this prototype will be published in October	
Evidence that the integration complements existing workflows rather than creating additional burden	Yes, in terms of design. User feedback from DataCite’s pilot is required.	

5. Community Solutions and Innovation Balance

Core Question: Are we effectively building on existing community work while developing necessary innovations?

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
Evidence of evaluating existing solutions or collaboration with developers of existing solutions	The matching strategy is based on Crossref’s Search Based Matching with Validation (SBMV) strategy and engaged with developer (Dominika Tkaczyk) during the project.	

Pilot Success Criteria	Evidence	Community Feedback
Specific justification for innovations as filling gaps	Filling the gap of matching <i>from</i> preprints <i>to</i> articles.	